

ABSTRACT

Demonetization has been a matter of discussion even after a gap of many years. Many researchers have done tremendous work on it. The impacts and outcomes are always in the centre of debate. This paper is an empirical research and in this, it is tried to find the impact of demonetization on banking system especially the growing NPAs. The other aspects demonetization were also discussed to correlate the impacts of note ban and growing Ns. Though the negative impacts are always discussed but this research focuses on many positive outcomes of demonetization. The role of banking system cannot be ignored as banks have been in a catalyst position throughout the process and period of demonetization.

The Indian commercial banking has witnessed various changes such as fraud cases, demonetization and sector sustainability during the study period year from 2009 – 2018, The paper focuses on to analyze affecting key drivers of Indian commercial banks bottom line. A sample of 30 banks was included, and ROA, R.O.E. and NIM were adopted as proxy variables to estimate profitability. The balanced panel data regression model was applied to achieve the desired objective.

The research outcomes depict the liquidity and asset management positively impacted both ROA and R.O.E., whereas, G.D.P., operational efficiency and demonetization negatively impacted ROA and R.O.E. As per NIM is concerned, inflation rate, asset management, capital adequacy ratio and asset quality have a substantially positive impact, and significant negative impact variables are G.D.P., deposit and operational efficiency. The implication aspect is that banks should focus on liquidity and deposits for proper utilization and better performance. When a bank has more credits than debit, it depicts higher yield assets which produce more profitability. This results in an adverse relation between banks profitability and liquidity, which is required in our study. For improving the profitability policymakers and regulators should consider macroeconomic factors.

The highly impacted period due to demonetization was experienced especially during November and December 2016. This impact was moderated prominently in the month of January 2017 and immoderate to a longer extent by mid of February 2017. As an impact of demonetization on Indian banks, there is a positive change in the financial statements of scheduled commercial banks. The quantum of amount deposited in the banks has raised and created surplus liquidity conditions. A significant increase in total number of accounts opened under the scheme of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yagna and the amount deposits in these accounts have also increased. A significant impact of demonetization has also been monitored in the use of electronic banking transactions. This study is descriptive in nature and the data has been taken for the period of pre-demonetization and post demonetization.

INTRODUCTION

There are several eminent economists who have not supported the government decision of demonetization of two higher denomination currencies together. On the other side, there are several eminent economists who have heartily supported and actively participated in implementing this as a step towards getting rid of corrupt, illegal, unaccounted money. Black money or unaccounted money was money that was not declared as income to the income tax authorities (Verma & Jain, 2017). The decision of demonetization was believed to have been taken to limit the enormous corruption and unrecorded or black money, and control the fake currency that often finances terror activities. The result of the demonetization was a situation of sufferings and distress with people standing in long queues in bank for exchanging their old currencies.

Due to these the same also affected in other banking business and services viz., disbursement of loan, new investment policy etc. This is not the first time that demonetization decision has been taken in India. Similar action was implemented twice before in 1946 and 1978. In 1946, the currency notes of ₹ 1,000 and ₹ 10,000 were removed from circulation. The second came in 1978 with ban the currency of ₹ 1000, ₹ 5000 and ₹ 10,000 out of circulation. Both the ban really did not have much adverse impact, as the currency of such higher denomination was not accessible to the common people and affected only the privileged few (Kulkarni & Tapas, 2017). Other countries have also tried it before and have experienced consequences of doing this. With respect to several positive and negative views of the respected economists and experts, the researchers may also believe that the process of recent demonetization may have impact on the efficiency level of banking industry. The present study is an initiative to analyze the same.

Deposits mobilisation by banks transforms households' and corporates' savings into productive capital for financing economic activity. Key to the efficiency of financial intermediation and core to banks' asset-liability management is the tenor and stability of deposit flows – since other sources of funds for banks depend on general liquidity conditions and are often of shorter duration than customer deposits. As a part of their deposit collection strategy, banks offer a range of products to suit the requirements of different stakeholders (corporates; households; non-residents; Government; financial sector entities) and population groups (rural; urban; semi-urban; metropolitan) – savings accounts that provide customers with the comfort of liquidity; fixed deposits that ensure more stable funds for banks at a relatively higher cost; and non-interest bearing current accounts that offer business-friendly banking services, often with overdraft facilities.

It is in this context that monitoring of the composition and ownership of deposit mobilization throws up valuable insights for designing appropriate policy responses in order to secure financial stability while ensuring adequate flows to productive sectors of the economy. Country practices reveal considerable diversity in regulatory and supervisory monitoring. For instance, the US Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation (FDIC) collects year-end deposit data from FDIC insured institutions, including insured US branches of foreign banks. On the other hand, the Bank of England conducts a bank liabilities survey on a quarterly basis. These data are useful in ascertaining changes in ownership patterns and other characteristics, and their findings are keenly analyzed for understanding underlying behavioral developments, typically of households (Summers, 1979; Calem and Carlino, 1991; Yener, et al., 2001; Vernikov, 2007; Han and Melecky, 2017).

CURRENT SCENARIO

Before I state anything, a clear picture of all the banks and ATMs is present which depicts today's reality. Long queues of people waiting for currency exchange or deposits outside the banks and for cash withdrawals outside ATMs. But definitely this is for a short time.

Many industries are going to be benefitted due to the demonetization policy and many are going to suffer. But overall the demand is going to or rather has already reduced by 30%-40% due to lack of money with the consumers. As the demand goes

down, the profits for the quarter ending December'16 is going to fall. The demand will catch the momentum as the dust settles down. The economy will stabilize as soon as there is enough new currency in the hands of people.

Effect of Demonetization on India's Financial Sector

Demonetization encouraged more Indians to have their own bank accounts while there were less incentives for the banking sector than expected. Before implementation of this policy, the development of the banking sector in India was out of proportion to its international economic status, with only half of the population using bank accounts and one in ten with access to bank credit. This, of course, could be attributed to India's vast urban and rural disparities, the wealth gap, traditional agricultural practices and poor infrastructure, but it also had to do with the underground economy and the people's lifestyle. Bank account used to be something new the rural Indians. Demonetization, however, forced them to open bank accounts. In short term, both the total number of financial transactions and its total value in India shot up. Financial transactions via debit card issued by the bank at ATMs in November 2016 rose by 42.9 percent compared with October . The total value of financial transactions done by the debit card issued by the bank at ATMs in November 2016 rose by 106.4 percent compared to those in October .

However, in the long term, there was only a slight increase of ATMs on site and off site, , implying the inability of demonetization to solve problems such as poor infrastructure and expansion of bank branches into the countryside. Jie Liang predicted that demonetization could improve financial services for the bottom class of India by opening up financing channels and reducing their financing costs, especially satisfying farmers' financial needs, as they always needed small loans in hard times . However, the situation didn't go as he had predicted, so far, at least. Agricultural credit growth appeared to have slowed after implementation of demonetization, probably as a result of damages to agricultural development caused by the policy itself and a lack of trust of the government from the public. Despite an upward trend last year, it is still not clear whether this was boosted by the recovery of the agricultural production or the decrease of loan cost for farmers. Perhaps only time can tell the truth.

IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION ON PROFITABILITY OF BANKS

Banks' net profits essentially reflect the difference between interest earned on loans and advances and investments, and interest paid on deposits and borrowings, adjusted for operating costs and provisions. Loans and advances and investments, which are the main sources of interest income, together constitute more than 85 per cent (61 per cent accounted for by loans and advances and 25 per cent by investments). The sharp increase of 4.1 percentage points in the share of CASA deposits in aggregate deposits to 39.3 per cent (up to February 17, 2017) resulted in a reduction in the cost of aggregate deposits. Banks have also lowered their term deposit rates; the median term deposit rate declined by 38 bps during November 2016-February 2017. The decline in the cost of funding resulted in decline in the 1-year median marginal cost of funds based lending rate (MCLR) by as much as 70 bps post-demonetization (November 2016-February 2017). Banks earned return of around 6.23-6.33 per cent under reverse repos and market stabilization scheme (MSS) as against the cost of CASA deposits of around 3.2 per cent.

Accordingly, for an average deployment of about ₹ 6 trillion in a quarter under reverse repos and MSS securities, banks' net interest income from increased deposits is estimated at about ₹ 45 billion in a quarter after demonetization. Banks continue to enjoy the increased share of low cost CASA deposits, although it is gradually declining with the increase in currency in circulation. The increase in net interest income would need to be adjusted for the cost of managing withdrawal of SBNs and injection of new bank notes (such as calibration of ATM machines, staff overtime, security arrangements, lower fees/waiver of fees on digital modes of payments), the exact details of which are not available at this stage.

IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION ON BALANCE SHEET OF BANKS

Decline in currency in circulation on account of demonetisation led to a surge in bank deposits. Total currency in circulation declined by about ₹ 8,800 billion (₹8.8 lac crores). This, in turn, was largely reflected in sharp increase of about ₹ 6,720 billion (₹ 6.72 lac crores) in aggregate deposits of the banking system even after outflows in NRI deposits during the period. Between end-December 2016 and early March 2017, there was a net increase in currency in circulation by about ₹ 2,600 billion. During this period, deposits with banks also declined moderately. As per data for October 28, 2016 (prior to demonetisation) and February 17, 2017 (latest available), aggregate deposits of SCBs increased by ₹ 5,549 billion during the period. Bulk of the deposits so mobilised by SCBs have been deployed in: (i) reverse repos of various tenors with the RBI; and (ii) cash management bills (CMBs) issued under the Market Stabilisation Scheme (which is a part of investment in government securities in the balance sheet of banks). Loans and advances

extended by banks increased by ₹ 1,008 billion. The incremental credit deposit ratio for the period was only 18.2 per cent. Additional deposits mobilised by commercial banks have been largely deployed in liquid assets. This may be due to the expected transitory nature of the bulk of such deposits and weak demand as reflected in the subdued growth of credit.

DEMONETIZATION AND BANK OPERATIONS

Demonetization has brought plethora of challenges in additions to the challenges which are already facing by Banks. The influences were short-term and long-term views. In short-term, it disrupted the banks and stressed strongly to carry out bank operations and in long run it helped the banks to pool the deposits without incurring of any cost. Here are four influences of demonetization on Banks.

- 1. Increase in Deposits:** Demonetization has increased the deposits in Banks. Unaccounted money in the form of Rs.500 and Rs.1000 were flowing to the Banks and the sizes of deposits have been increased. It helped the banks to grab the deposits and increase their deposits.
- 2. Fall in cost of Funds:** Over the past few months, the deposits are increased. It led the banks to keep a major part of deposits in the form of cash deposits. PSU Banks have a lion share (over 70%) of the deposits and biggest gainers of the rise in deposits, leading to lower cost of funds.
- 3. Demand for Government Bonds:** After sharp rise in deposits on post demonetization, banks started lending such surplus deposits to the RBI under the reverse repo options. PSU Banks, particularly, deployed excess funds in government bonds. The return on bond investment is likely to add 15 to 20 per cent increase in the earnings of banks.
- 4. Sagginess in Lending:** lending growth of the banks is considerably less even after demonetization and its impact of growth in the amount of public deposit. Banks have tried to lend the money to the needy group by reducing their interest rates, but it shrunk over the last few months.
- 5. Free flow of deposits:** Banks have gained deposits substantially after demonetization which they can invest.
- 6. Cash Reserve Requirement:** 100% CRR on incremental deposits meant that banks did not earn any interest on Rs. 3 Lakh crore of deposits for nearly a fortnight.
- 7. Waived off ATM Charges:** ATM charges were waived off during banned note exchange and banks incurred a loss of Rs. 20 in every transaction.

Demonetization in India Towards A Cashless Economy

While it is practically impossible to have a 100% cashless economy , the proportion of hard cash in the economy will decrease and our economy will get more digitized . This will result in greater transparency . Now government has put Some limitation for Cash Withdraw from bank Accounts.

People Will go for online payments. They Will use PayTM Or other online payment to companies for Buying goods or Making payments. More Use of Debit and Credit.

Effects of Demonetization in India Rush at Banks

Banks will be extremely over-crowded by people . People will forget everything else and throng to the places where the banned notes are being officially exchanged leading to a tremendous chaos

DATA INTERPRETATION

1. Do you think Demonetization is having a positive impact over banking sector?

Interpretation:

By analyzing the data, it was ascertained that, 55% of the employees have supported that monetization had a positive impact on the banking sector. Where about only 9-10 % of the employees were seeing some sort of bad effects and showed disagreement. Demonetization brought cashless system and it had encouraged the bank staff and made their work easy with more efficiency. The main reason to go cashless was the ease in performing the financial transactions.

2. There is an impact on online banking due to demonetization?

Interpretation:

The employees said that most of the people are now a day's using mobile applications to do the banking activities. 51% of the employees had a positive response about the effect of demonetization on the online banking sector. The application named "M connect plus" is being effectively used by the customers to do online money transfer. Cashless transactions provide benefits for online banking as users save their time and efforts to come to bank personally for their day to day bank transactions.

3. Do you think Government has not prepared enough for the post demonetization situation?

Interpretation

After analyzing the whole process of demonetization a mixed opinion was developed about the preparations of the government. Some of the employees favored the governments' steps, while others had a completely opposite view. As demonetization occur within a short span of time without giving time to react as it was a secret disclosure, so it leads to mismanagement among bank employees. They had to work day night to maintain the transactions and providing service to their customers to exchange

their old notes. This made post demonetization a little difficult for bank employees to react as they were not well prepared enough to tackle it.

4. What is the impact of Demonetization on cash flow in banks?

Interpretation

Through the responses of this question we can see that the cash flow in banks has reduced we believe that it has happened because the people are now making cashless transactions and the RBI has not issued enough currency to match the previous flow in cash.

5. What is the impact of Demonetization on interest rate?

Interpretation

Through the responses of this question we can see that the Interest Rate has Decreased post demonetization. SBI Chairman Arundhati Bhattacharya said that all the rates will fall post demonetization. There are high inflows of deposits in banks but the demand of credit has decreased. Thus resulting in the fall of rates but after a period. Though the fall in the rates is not large but it still helps.

6. What is the Impact of demonetization on money lending?

Interpretation

By analyzing the responses of this question we have noticed that money lending has decreased post Demonetization. Demonetization has led to cash shortage which has dented the demand for loans. Banks don't have resources to provide these loans.

After demonetization banks focused on exchanging currency and were not providing loans. All the bank staff are busy in exchanging currency they have no time for providing loans. Arundhati Bhattacharya, Chairperson, SBI said that all rates will fall. The bank has seen high inflow of deposits but the demand of credit has decreased.

7. What is the impact of Demonetization on the use of online banking?

Interpretation

Through this question we can understand that the use of online banking has increased after demonetization. In India people were mostly dependent on cash transactions but after demonetization when the supply of money was less people are resorting to the use of online banking

and online payments to meet their daily expenses. Thus we can say that the use of online banking has increased after demonetization.

8. What is the impact of Demonetization on the use of plastic cards?

Interpretation

Through the responses of this question we can interpret that all of the people believe that demonetization has increased the use of plastic cards. Due to the decrease in the supply of cash because of demonetization most of the people have resorted to the use of online banking,

9. What is the impact of Demonetization on opening of new accounts?

Interpretation

Through the responses of this question we can see that people believe that new accounts are opening post demonetization. For depositing money in the banks account after demonetization new accounts are opened.

10. What is the impact of Demonetization on the no of customers in branches?

Interpretation

The responses of this question tell us that the number of customers in the branches have increased after demonetization. Whether it is to deposit the old currency, open new accounts or to collect the new currency all the branches and ATMs are flooded with.

11. Do you think that there was an impact of Demonetization on banking sector?

Interpretation

This research was conducted to find the “IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION ON THE BANKING SECTOR”, at the end of this research we can say that Demonetization does have an impact on the banking sector.

CONCLUSION

Demonetization is a tool used by central government to fight against corruption and black money. In the same path, it influenced and brought changes in all the corner of the economy. Banks are major institutions affected by demonetization. Banned denominations were ploughed back and allowed the

citizens to exchange with the banks. While exchanging, it disturbed temporarily and influenced its regular operations. Though it affected badly to major extent of bank operations, it helped the economy to find growth and development of the country through financial institutions like Banks. The series of currency will not be acceptable as valid currency. The demonetization was done in Nov 2016 in as an effort to stop counterfeiting of the current currency notes allegedly used for funding terrorism, as well as a crackdown on black money in the country. Demonetization is a generations' memorable experience and is going to be one of the economic events of our time. Its impact is felt by every Indian citizen. Demonetization affects the economy through the liquidity side. Its effect will be a telling one because nearly 86% of currency value in circulation was withdrawn without replacing bulk of it. As a result of the withdrawal of Rs 500 and Rs 1000 notes, there occurred huge gap in the currency composition as after Rs 100; Rs 2000 is the only denomination.